

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

CHARACTERISATION OF THE WRINKLING BEHAVIOUR OF A BIAXIAL NON-CRIMP FABRIC DURING FORMING

J.V. Viisainen^{*}, J. Zhou, and M.P.F. Sutcliffe

Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, UK

UNIVERSITY OF
CAMBRIDGE

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

* Corresponding author (jvv21@cam.ac.uk)

#ICCM22

Defects during Pre-forming are a Major Obstacle for use of RTM for Composite Manufacturing

- Defects during preforming:
 - Affect component quality
 - Make production slower
 - Increase costs of RTM significantly
- It is required to understand how these various defects develop so that they can be minimised or eliminated
- **Wrinkles** are a critical defect that have had significant attention in academia and in industry

Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process

P. Boisse. Woven Composites, chapter 7. Imperial College Press, London, 1st edition, 2015

Prodromou & Chen (1997) – Wrinkling in Woven Fabrics due to locking at critical shear angle

- Pivotal analytical study in the field of fabric wrinkling
 - Postulates that woven fabrics wrinkle when they exceed a critical shear angle at which the tows 'lock up'
- Since then, most work in the field has focused their efforts on measuring shear angle in order to predict wrinkling

Hypothesis for onset of wrinkling in woven fabrics

A. G. Prodromou and J. Chen, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 28, pp. 491–503, 1997.

Allaoui et al (2011) – No wrinkling beyond critical locking angle for woven fabric over tetrahedron

- The first work that began to doubt the conclusions made by Prodromou & Chen
- Their results clearly showed that wrinkling does not necessarily occur for woven fabrics when the critical locking angle is exceeded

No wrinkling for shear angle of 60° even though critical shear for fabric angle is 40°

Zone of maximum shear angle in woven fabric after forming over a tetrahedron

S. Allaoui *et al.*, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 612–622, 2011.

Boisse (2018) – Wrinkles occur due to a combination of tension, shear and bending

Hemispherical forming with: a) Tensile stiffness only
b) Tensile and shear stiffnesses only c) Tensile, shear and bending stiffnesses d) Experimental forming

P. Boisse et al., *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 141, pp. 234–249, 2018.

Boisse elaborates on this further in their recent work:

- Shear (locking) angle is not sufficient to determine wrinkling onset
- Other strains (tension, bending) also play a critical role
- Wrinkles are given by the solution of the global dynamic virtual work equation:

$$W_{\text{ext}}(\eta) - W_{\text{int}}^{\text{tens}}(\eta) - W_{\text{int}}^{\text{shear}}(\eta) - W_{\text{int}}^{\text{bend}}(\eta) = W_{\text{acc}}(\eta)$$

Predicting Wrinkling of Non-Crimp Fabrics

- Most work thus far on wrinkling has focused on woven fabrics but how do these developments extend to non-crimp fabrics (NCFs)?
- We need to be able to understand this ever more important type of textile reinforcement given its wide potential for applications in automotive and aerospace industries

Key Questions to Address:

1. **How can we predict wrinkling in non-crimp fabrics? Is shear angle an useful indicator of wrinkling in this case?**
2. **How do biaxial NCFs wrinkle and how can we characterise this behaviour?**

BMW i3: Cabin made from NCFs using RTM process (*Amazon*)

Wrinkle Characterisation of NCFs in the Literature

Chen et al (2016):

- Wrinkling treated as a binary phenomenon
- Wrinkles in NCFs tend to occur in regions of high shear angle

Experimental Forming Setup

(a) Tool setup

(b) Dimensions

Discrete deformation tracking approach

(a) Undeformed fabric

(b) Deformed fabric

Arnold et al (2016):

- Wrinkle amplitude measured at discrete intervals using 'Shape from Focus'
- Characterised using RMS wrinkle amplitude
- Increasing blank holder force reduces wrinkling

Forming rig

Wrinkle amplitude calculation procedure

Outline of Presentation

1. Material Overview
2. Experimental Methodology
3. Post Processing Procedure
4. Results
 1. Wrinkle Prediction
 2. Wrinkle Characterisation
5. Conclusions

Conclusions of Study

1. The presence or growth of **wrinkling** in NCFs **cannot be predicted** through observing the fabric's **shear angle**
2. The **wrinkling behaviour of NCFs** for a particular forming geometry **can be characterised** through the onset point of wrinkling, the maximum wrinkle amplitude and maximum wrinkle area

1. Material Overview

- Product name: HiMax™ CGL4790 - FCIM359
- Manufactured by Hexcel
- Biaxial $[-45^\circ/45^\circ]$ NCF
- Comprised of:
 - Carbon fibre (24k) tows
 - Polyester Pillar stitching along 0° direction

Fabric architecture (Hexcel)

Front view of fabric

Asymmetric shear behaviour:
Shearing restricted in positive
shear due to stitching

Shear characterisation of FCIM359 using picture frame test

S. Chen et al., *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 91, pp. 156–167, 2016.

2. Experimental Methodology

1) Sample Preparation

2) Forming Test

2. Experimental Methodology

1) Sample Preparation

- Speckle pattern is required on the surface of the NCF to allow tracking via 3D-DIC
- Repeatabile speckle pattern application controlled through:
 - Constant spray distance
 - Constant spray pressure
 - Constant spraying speed/motion

2. Experimental Methodology

1) Sample Preparation

- Graphite powder spray can increase the bending stiffness of the NCF
- Critical to ensure a controlled and repeatable spray application such that the effect is minimised while reducing reflections satisfactorily
- Cantilever test (ASTM D1388) used to determine the optimal conditions for spraying
 - e.g. Graphite spraying distance of 500 mm

Effect of Graphite Spraying Distance on Bending Stiffness

2. Experimental Methodology

2) Forming Test

- NCF formed over a benchmark geometry using in-house forming rig while tracked by Aramis 3D DIC system
- Continuous tracking of wrinkle development and shear angle
- Blank holder force (BHF) applied using hanging weights
- Repeatability ensured through
 - Fabric alignment guides
 - Constant forming velocity using linear actuator

For all tests:

- Maximum Punch Displacement = 75 mm
- Forming Speed = 1 mm/s
- Initial fabric alignment:

11 - Top tow direction
22 - Bottom tow direction
00 - Stich direction

Experimental forming setup

3. Post Processing Procedure

Wrinkle Amplitude (a_w)

Wrinkle Area (A_w)

Shear Angle (γ)

Out of Plane Displacement

Smoothed Out of Plane Displacement

Wrinkle Area = % of surface that has wrinkled

Fibre directions obtained through interpolation from DIC data

$$A_w = \frac{\text{\# of Surface Points where } |a_w| > 1 \text{ mm}}{\text{Total \# of Surface Points}}$$

Hemispherical Punch

Wrinkle Area shown for NCF Formed Over Hemisphere

- Not Wrinkled
- Wrinkled

- Initial state
- Deformed state

$$\gamma = \frac{\pi}{2} - \alpha$$

Wrinkle Amplitude [a)-b)]

Absolute Wrinkle Amplitude

'Maximum Wrinkle Amplitude'
= Mean of largest 500 absolute amplitudes

4. Results

Two types of wrinkles develop during forming

Can be tracked by DIC

Cannot be tracked by DIC

Biaxial NCF formed over a hemisphere

4.1 Wrinkle Prediction

Can wrinkling be predicted using shear angle?

- Maximum shear angle growth correlates well with maximum wrinkle amplitude over the course of the forming process (approximately linear relationship)

Max Wrinkle Amplitude Development

Max Shear Angle Development

Wrinkle-Shear Relationship

- However, maximum shearing does not necessarily occur where the largest wrinkles occur.

4.1 Wrinkle Prediction

- Considering the development of **shear angle at the location** of maximum wrinkle amplitude:
 - Maximum shearing does not occur at locations of maximum wrinkling
 - Wrinkles start developing before any significant shearing
 - **No clear relationship** between shear angle and wrinkle amplitude can be deduced

4.1 Wrinkle Prediction

Wrinkles even develop in locations with negligible shearing

Wrinkle Amplitude Map

- Wrinkles develop all around the circumference, even in regions where there is no shearing.
- Large shearing is only evident in the top and bottom regions of the fabric (where shearing is not restricted by stitching).

Shear Angle Map

4.1 Wrinkle Prediction

Four Benchmark Geometries

- Do the observations made about wrinkle amplitude and shear angle hold for different punch geometries?

Triangular Prism

Tetrahedron

Double Dome

Hemisphere

Sharp edged

Rounded

- All punch geometries have been manufactured such that their height is 75 mm, thus allowing for comparisons to be made

4.1 Wrinkle Prediction

Triangular Prism

Tetrahedron

Double Dome

Hemisphere

Wrinkle Amplitude Map

Shear Angle Map

- Yes, the observations hold for these four different geometries
 - For all four geometries, some of the wrinkles grow in regions of negligible shearing

4.2 Wrinkle Characterisation

Triangular Prism

Hemisphere

Tetrahedron

Double Dome

Max Wrinkle Amplitude Development

- Rounded geometries exhibit different wrinkling patterns to sharp edged geometries

Wrinkling onset point taken as the PD when $a_w=1$

4.2 Wrinkle Characterisation

Wrinkling Comparison Between Geometries

- The triangular prism wrinkles earliest and has the largest wrinkle area
- The tetrahedron has the largest maximum wrinkle amplitude
- The double dome wrinkles the least with latest wrinkle onset point

Punch Displacement at Wrinkling Onset

Maximum Wrinkle Amplitude

Maximum Wrinkle Area

Triangular Prism

Tetrahedron

Double Dome

Hemisphere

5. Conclusions

1. The presence or growth of wrinkling in NCFs cannot be predicted through observing the fabric's shear angle.
2. The wrinkling behaviour of NCFs for a particular forming geometry can be characterised through considering the maximum wrinkle amplitude and percentage wrinkle area.

5. Conclusions + Observations

1. The presence or growth of wrinkling in NCFs cannot be predicted through observing the fabric's shear angle.
 - Wrinkling behavior highly dependent on forming geometry and process conditions.
 - Shearing behavior dependent largely on fabric architecture (shear regions form along fibre directions).
2. The wrinkling behaviour of NCFs for a particular forming geometry can be characterised through considering the maximum wrinkle amplitude and percentage wrinkle area.
 - There is a definite wrinkling onset point after which wrinkles grow approximately linearly. The onset point is variable based on geometry.
 - Sharp edged geometries wrinkle more significantly compared to rounded geometries.